

incorporated after application except at panicle initiation. USG was applied after seedling establishment at 10-12 cm soil depth. All treatments received 20-30-20 kg PKS/ha. Test variety was BR3.

Application of N as prilled urea (PU)

or as USG significantly improved panicle number/m² and grain yield over no N (see table). Deep point placement of USG resulted in significantly higher grain yield than split application of PU.

Further increase in grain yield, better N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N), and higher apparent N recovery occurred when the hole was closed after USG application. □

Disease management

Occurrence of rice sheath blight (ShB) *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn on rice panicles in India

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Rice ShB (*Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn) normally attacks the leaf sheath and leaf blade. We found characteristic symptoms of the disease at the time of panicle emergence. Affected panicles were a chaffy, greyish brown, cylindrical rod matted together by the mycelium of the fungus (see figure). Many white and mustard seed-like, brown sclerotia that

formed on the diseased panicle were easily detached. The fungus easily infected rachis and its branches but could not affect the panicle neck.

Sclerotia from the infected panicles were collected and isolated on potato dextrose agar. Mycelium is white, and septate. Its internodal area range was 20 × 120-40 × 350 μm. Sclerotia are more or less globose, white when young, then becoming dark brown. Individual sclerotium measured up to 4 mm, but could clump in culture to form a larger sclerotia.

Spraying mycelium fragments prepared from 5-d-old culture on just emerged panicles, leaves, and leaf sheaths of susceptible rice variety IR50 induced disease symptoms similar to those of rice ShB. Spraying IR50 plants with sterile water did not induce disease. □

Rice panicles infected with *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn in India.

Device for field measurement of conidia release by a single leaf blast lesion

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In the study of the life cycle of rice blast fungus *Pyricularia oryzae*, measurement under field conditions of the conidia released from a single lesion is important in understanding conidia dispersal pattern. Some preliminary experiments to improve spore catch efficiency were done during the 1985 crop season in Korea. Using those results, we devised a new KY type spore trap (see figure).

The KY type spore trap. Korea, 1985